

IPBES VA Chapter 4. Coincidence of Aichi target 2 reporting and valuation at country level / IPBES values assessment (4.11)

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Description

This review corresponds to the IPBES values assessment. Its purpose was to explore whether a higher frequency of valuation studies (of ecosystem services / nature's contributions to people) in a country is associated with the likelihood of uptake of valuation by national government agencies. The analysis used two indicators to proxy the uptake of scientific valuation knowledge at national scale: (i) likelihood of ecosystem accounting implementation at national level indicated by the system of environmental economic accounting and ecosystem accounting (SEEA EA), and (ii) likelihood of reporting Aichi target 2 progress in national biodiversity strategies and action plans under the CBD (Aichi target 2 "By 2020, at the latest, biodiversity values have been integrated into national and local development and poverty reduction strategies and planning processes and are being incorporated into national accounting, as appropriate, and reporting systems").

Process overview

miro

Protocol

Type of analysis/search/review: analysis of information collected from three different sources on (1) valuation studies, (2) reporting of progress on Aichi target 2 and (3) SEEA EA implementation, at the national level.

Details regarding information on the number of valuation studies conducted by country:

This data was obtained from the literature corpus used for the uptake review in chapter 4¹. Valuation study frequency per country was grouped into categorical variables: very limited valuation research (<100 studies), limited (100-200 studies), some (200-1000) or high (>1000 studies), based on an analysis of discretization ranges that best correlated with the uptake variables (discretization tool in Hugin software).

Details regarding information reports on progress on Aichi target 2:

This data corresponds to the reports by country updated until January 2021, obtained by courtesy of the CBD Secretariat, and which was not accessible online. The information presents more countries

¹ Systematic review on valuation uptake ([10.5281/zenodo.4391335](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4391335)).

reporting on the progress for this target and uses different categories for the progress reported, than what is accessible online through the CBD website (<https://www.cbd.int/aichi-targets/target/2>). It was decided to use this data given that it was the most up to date until the moment of the review. For our analysis we have interpreted “partial implementation” in the data provided by the CBD Secretariat as an "insufficient rate" relative to the Aichi target #2, based on the CBDs website classification of "partial implementation".

Details regarding information on SEEA implementation:

Data about the implementation of the System of Environmental Economic Accounting-Central Framework (SEEA CF), the System of Environmental Economic Accounting-Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA EA), both of them, or neither, is taken from the 2020 Global Assessment Results. These results are available through the System of Environmental Economic Accounting website (<https://seea.un.org/content/2020-global-assessment-results-1>).

Treatment applied: Given that the list of countries for which data was reported was different among sources, homologation was performed before analysing the information. That process considered the list of countries used for all IPBES assessments and does not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area or of its authorities, or concerning the delimitation of its frontiers or boundaries. Results of the analysis are presented in section 4.6.4.1 *Coincidence of Aichi target 2 reporting and valuation at country level*, where specifically *Figure 4.15* provides a visualisation of the data and correlations at country level. Report of further statistical analysis and results are presented in *annex 4.8*.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_4.11_05-2021_(A)	csv	17 KB	Data collected from three different sources on (1) valuation studies, (2) reporting of progress on Aichi target 2 and (3) SEEA EA implementation.